

Task 30

SHORT
ROTATION
CROPS for
BIOENERGY
SYSTEMS

TECHNICAL
REVIEW NO.4

Willow short rotation
coppice commercially
grown on agricultural
land in Sweden

- possibilities for
improvement of
biodiversity and
landscape design.

Short Rotation Crops for Bioenergy Systems

www.shortrotationcrops.org

Definition: “Short Rotation Crops

“Short Rotation Crops” means woody crops such as Willows, Poplars, Robinia and *Eucalyptus* with coppicing abilities as well as lignocellulosic crops such as Reed canary grass, Switchgrass and *Miscanthus*

Objective:

The objective of the Task is to acquire, synthesise and transfer theoretical and practical knowledge of sustainable short rotation biomass production systems and thereby to enhance market development and large-scale implementation in collaboration with the various sectors involved.

Themes:

- Linking producers and markets
- SRC: Climate change and ecosystem services
- Improving and optimising production systems
- Energy, agriculture and environmental policies for SRC
- Competition for land and water resources

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Technical Review No. 4

Willow short rotation coppice commercially grown on agricultural land in Sweden - possibilities for improvement of biodiversity and landscape design.

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Summary

The report presents the results from an investigation, in which the objectives were to (i) assess the possibilities of short rotation willow plantations to improve environmental qualities and the design of agricultural landscape, and (ii) evaluate how plantations of *Salix* should be localized and managed in order to support some of the Swedish environmental objectives. In addition, potential conflicts of interest should be identified, e.g., between economic constraints requiring maximized biomass yields on one hand and environmental concerns on the other hand.

The methods included a literature survey and a questionnaire, which was sent out to central and regional authorities, non-governmental organizations (environmental, bio-energy, landscape architecture), research institutes (university) and selected companies dealing with, or having an interest in, *Salix* business. A balanced synthesis of results was attempted by considering the opinions of various experts and authorities.

Plantations of *Salix* and other fast-growing trees grown on agricultural land can improve biodiversity at landscape level, in particular if the plantations are established instead of cultures of cereals and spruce or fallow ground in a homogeneous agricultural landscape. Plantations of *Salix* can also positively affect soil properties compared to conventional agriculture. Particularly plantations of relatively small size can improve the aesthetic perception of homogeneous agricultural landscapes by adding variation and structure.

Opinions of central and regional authorities, non-governmental organizations etc. regarding the plantation of willow on agricultural land are often strongly biased due to incorrect knowledge on *Salix* culture and its effects on the environment. There is a large body of knowledge covering many years on how plantations should be localized and managed in order to favour environmental and landscape qualities. However, this knowledge is rarely applied in commercial *Salix* culture in Sweden. Campaigns and guidelines to disseminate valid information on *Salix* culture and its effects on the environment to authorities and the public, as well as improved communication among authorities, will help to remedy the common lack of correct information.

Regarding the location of plantations, no serious conflicts between commercial and environmental *Salix* culture are expected if the willows are planted outside areas of high nature or culture conservation value. Synergy effects are possible if plantations are located near to native woods. With respect to plantation management, the commercial practice of *Salix* culture might frequently conflict with the interests of nature and culture conservationists. An active dialogue between commercial *Salix* growers and nature/culture conservationists will facilitate feasible compromises between the two sides.

Plantations of *Salix* can contribute to reach some of the Swedish environmental objectives such as 'Reduced Climate Impact', 'A Non-Toxic Environment', 'A Varied Agricultural Landscape' and 'A Rich Diversity of Plant and Animal Life'. However, some actions in support of particular environmental objectives could potentially conflict with actions in support of others. For example, maximized biomass yield in willow plantations maximizes also carbon sequestration and, therefore, supports the environmental objective 'Reduced Climate Impact'. However, management actions supporting maximized biomass yield can lower biodiversity and, therefore, conflict with the environmental objectives 'A Varied Agricultural Landscape' and 'A Rich Diversity of Plant and Animal Life'. A mosaic of plantations with different primary goals, e.g., purely commercial or environmental, probably would contribute most to reach the Swedish environmental objectives.

Preface

The use of biofuels from agricultural land is expected to increase in Sweden and worldwide. In Sweden, the complete production chain for biomass from *Salix* plantations on agricultural land is well developed and enables a profitable production. In addition, economic support for these plantations is available in the framework of the EU's common agricultural policy.

An increased area of *Salix* plantations can contribute positively to a number of the Swedish environmental objectives (*miljömål*), but also may bring about conflicts of interest both within and between different targets for environmental objectives. One possibility to achieve the environmental objective 'Reduced Climate Impact' is an increased production of biofuels to replace fossil fuels. Also the objectives 'Zero Eutrophication' and 'A Non-Toxic Environment' can benefit from an increased area of *Salix* plantations by means of the great capacity of fast-growing trees to take up nitrogen and other substances from the ground. An important question then becomes how to not only avoid conflicts between some of the relevant environmental objectives, but also make use of possible synergies linked to, e.g., the objectives of 'A Rich Farmland' and 'A Rich Flora and Fauna'.

This report summarises an attitude and literature survey which, from the commercial, nature conservation and landscape design perspectives highlights both positive opportunities and potential conflicts of interest that an increased area of *Salix* plantations on agricultural land can lead to. It summarizes the results of an investigation that I worked with on behalf of the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (*Naturvårdsverket*) during 2005 and 2006. The report is a modified version of the original report to the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (Weih 2006).

Background

High density plantations of *Salix* and other fast-growing tree species on agricultural land are currently discussed as an interesting possibility to partly replace fossil fuels and at the same time give farmers in many regions of the world a new perspective for a future in which food production on agricultural land probably will greatly decrease. In Sweden, the culture of willow has been most important during recent years and in contrast to most other countries in the world, complete biomass chains for the commercial production of biomass from willow short rotation plantations are in place.

Figure 1: Plantations of *Salix* grow usually 6-8 m high before harvested, but the individual shoots can grow more than 5 m in a single year in good conditions. Harvesting takes place in winter every three to five years, after which new shoots grow up. Photo: Å. Augustson (left) and N.-E. Nordh (right)

Also other fast-growing trees can be grown on agricultural land for energy purpose and in Sweden, there is currently increasing interest in the culture of poplar and hybrid aspen (genus *Populus*) (Karacic *et al.* 2003, Borgman 2005). Today, *Populus* is agriculturally grown only in a few plantations in Southern Sweden, whereas the area of willow plantations on agricultural land in Sweden is around 15000 ha. The plant material used for the plantations are *Salix* hybrids produced by a breeding company and the major species used in the Swedish breeding program are *S. viminalis* and *S. dasyclados*, but *S. schwerinii*, *S. triandra*, *S. caprea*, *S. daphnoides* and *S. ericocephala* are also used (Kuzovkina *et al.* 2008). A willow plantation may last up to 30 years, with biomass harvests every third to fifth year. A *Populus* plantation is commonly harvested at 10 to 15 years intervals. Thus, even under the cool-temperate to boreal climate in Sweden, fast-growing trees are harvested at much shorter intervals compared to the felling scheme for deciduous trees in traditional forestry (Weih 2004).

Plantations of fast-growing trees on agricultural land are commonly established for energy purposes, but also for phytoremediation of municipal waste water, landfill leachate, log-yard runoff, sewage sludge and wood-ash (Aronsson and Perttu 2001, Dimitriou and Aronsson 2005). In future lignocellulosic biomass is expected to increasingly replace oil as raw material for a great range of products including transport fuels

(“biorefinery concept”). Therefore, the area of agricultural land planted with fast-growing trees will most probably greatly increase in the future.

Nevertheless, during recent years, the development of *Salix* culture in Sweden was slower than desired considering the possibilities of willow plantations to replace fossil fuels and also to reduce ground water contamination by agricultural residues. In Sweden, the stagnation in development is not caused by technical barriers, rather than non-technical barriers such as ignorance of best-practice advice in existing commercial plantations, negative public attitudes and the dominance of a single actor on the market (Helby *et al.* 2004, IEA 2005, Hoffmann and Weih 2005). Still, an increase to about 200000 ha, which corresponds to almost 10% of the agricultural land in Sweden, is envisaged until 2015 by the Swedish Energy Agency (Energimyndigheten 2001). In addition, life cycle analysis of willow biomass production on agricultural land based on commercial varieties and cultivation practices in Sweden revealed high energy efficiency of the production system: The produced biomass yields 20 times more energy compared to the energy input, a figure which is more than 3 times higher than the energy balance (i.e., energy output / energy input) of annual energy crops such as wheat and rape (Börjesson 2006).

In general, plantations of fast-growing trees can have both positive and negative effects on the environment, depending on location and management of the plantation (WWF 2003). In a similar way, an increase in *Salix* plantations may be positive or negative with respect to the Swedish environmental objectives (<http://www.miljomal.nu>) and the general perception of landscape, depending on where the plantations are located and how they are managed (Naturvårdsverket 2003, Skärbäck and Becht 2005). Hence, there is a great need for better knowledge on how plantations of fast-growing trees should be located and managed in order to not only avoid negative impact on biodiversity, landscape and cultural heritage, but also improve the possibilities for positive effects of the plantations on these values. The report presents the results from an evaluation, inquired by the Swedish Nature Protection Agency, in which the objectives were to

- (i) assess the possibilities of short rotation willow plantations to improve environmental qualities and the design of agricultural landscape, and

- (ii) evaluate how plantations of *Salix* should be localized and managed in order to support some of the Swedish environmental objectives. In addition, potential conflicts of interest should be identified, e.g., between economic constraints requiring maximized biomass yields on one hand and environmental concerns on the other hand. The methods included a literature survey and a questionnaire, which was sent out to central and regional authorities, non-governmental organizations (environmental, bio-energy, landscape architecture), research institutes (university) and selected companies dealing with, or having an interest in, *Salix* business. A balanced synthesis of results as well as a sound basis for future development of *Salix* culture in relation to environment and landscape was attempted by considering the opinions of various experts and authorities.

Relevant Authorities

The commercial culture *Salix* is today almost only performed on agricultural (as opposed to forest) land and the Swedish Board of Agriculture (*Jordbruksverket*) is responsible for rules regarding agricultural land use and subsidies. As a potential energy crop, *Salix* research and development is supported by the Swedish Energy Agency (*Energimyndigheten*). The culture of *Salix* on agricultural land affects the environment and sustainability of natural resources exploitation and use and is thereby linked to the Swedish environmental objectives, for which the Swedish Nature Protection Agency (*Naturvårdsverket*) has overall responsibility. The culture of perennial crops replacing traditional (annual) crops may also influence landscape and cultural heritage, for which the Swedish National heritage Board (*Riksantikvarieämbetet*) has particular responsibility. Although the Swedish Forest Agency (*Skogsstyrelsen*) has no responsibility for the culture of *Salix* on agricultural land, this agency has responsibility for the products generated by *Salix* culture, i.e., wood fuels. The Swedish Forest Board (and other organisations) offers the establishment of "Green plans" for forest properties – the "Green plans" are accepted as a basis for both FSC and PEFC certification¹ – but currently the regulation system is only applied for forest properties and not applicable for plantations of fast-growing trees on agricultural land. From an economical perspective and also with respect to sustainability thinking, it might be advantageous to establish multifunctional plantations, in which the capacity of fast-growing trees to effectively absorb and heavy metal absorption is utilised (Aronsson and Perttu 2001; Rosenqvist and Ness 2004). If willow plantations are used for phytoremediation of heavy metal contaminated soils or other waste products, the responsibilities of the National Board of Health and Welfare (*Socialstyrelsen*), the Swedish Institute for Infectious Disease Control (*Smittskyddsinstitutet*), the National Board of Housing, Building and Planning (*Boverket*) or the Swedish Chemical Agency (*Kemikalieinspektionen*) might be involved. Finally, the nature conservation, cultural heritage, agriculture and health service units of the county administration boards might be involved in the planning and establishment of willow plantations on agricultural land.

Very obviously, a large number of different central and regional authorities might be dealing with the various aspects of willow culture on agricultural land. My impression is that coordination of the different interests is performed only at a very minor degree. In addition, critical problems related to, e.g., the use of sewage sludge and ashes in willow plantations are frequently delegated among different authorities and none of the involved organisations seems to be willing to take the overall responsibility for solving the problem (P. Aronsson, SLU, pers. comm.). The result is often that the overall process is seriously hampered and that the lack of any part taking the overall responsibility leads to a fight between partial interests. This implies that any holistic or integrated perspective is practically impossible, possibilities for synergies are minimised and major focus is on the contrasting partial interests, rather than the possibilities for compromises and improvements.

¹ FSC (Forest Stewardship Council) and PEFC (Pan-European Forest Certification) are certification systems for environmentally friendly, sustainable and socially accepted forestry practice. See www.fsc.org/en and www.pefc.org/

Certification Systems

During recent years, many attempts have been made to define sustainability and sustainable forestry and most of the definitions are based on sustainability standards consisting of principles, criteria and/or indicators (see Lewandowski and Faaj 2006 for an overview of relevant certification systems). Some of the standards, for example ITTO (International Tropical Timber Organization, Criteria and indicators for sustainable management of natural tropical forests)² contain criteria and indicators that can be used to measure trends in plantation or forest management, but without the ambition to classify the plantations or forests in terms of “bad” or “good” ones. These standards can be valuable tools for development of national policies regarding forestry principles and recommendations, but the standards cannot be used for certification of forestry (or tree plantation) products. In contrast to the above standards, others, for example FSC (Forest Stewardship Council Principles and Criteria)³, define strict criteria that a (plantation) forest property and the products from this property must comply with in order to be labelled “sustainable forestry”. Standards according to FSC and PEFC (see Page 6) are applied in Sweden for products grown on forest land and the standards are implemented by means of “Green plans” that the owner of the property establishes together with the Swedish Forestry Agency. In Sweden, willow plantations grown on agricultural land are currently not eligible for certification according to FSC or PEFC rules. Indeed, the establishment and management of plantations of fast-growing trees on agricultural land has more in common with agricultural crops than forestry, and these plantations need to be regarded as agricultural crops, rather than forestry systems. However, standards equivalent to FSC or PEFC, but applied to agricultural crops (e.g., Swedish Seal of Quality, *Svenskt Sigill*) have so far never been applied to perennial crops such as *Salix* plantations on agricultural land.

Different Perspectives on *Salix* Culture

The use of fossil fuels probably contributes a major portion to the global greenhouse effect both in Sweden and world-wide. In order to achieve the Swedish environmental objective ‘Reduced Climate Impact’⁴, one would need to increase the share of renewable energy sources in Sweden, for example, by an enhanced area of *Salix* biomass plantations on agricultural land. Commercial plantations of fast-growing trees are usually established and managed for purely economic purposes and location, design and management are made accordingly. This implies that short transport distances from the plantation to the biomass user (i.e., heat and power plants) and easy access with heavy machinery (e.g., harvesters) will guide the choice of location, optimum harvest conditions will guide the design of plantations, and maximized biomass yield will guide the management of these commercial plantations.

The culture of fast-growing trees is today also discussed as a means to sequester carbon and thereby counteract the increasing global greenhouse effect (see Grogan and Matthews 2002 for *Salix*). The carbon sequestration potential increases strongly with the biomass production in a plantation (Weih and Van Bussel 2006). In

² www.itto.or.jp/live/PageDisplayHandler?pagelid=2001

³ www.fsc.org/en/about/policy_standards/princ_criteria/12

⁴ www.miljomal.nu

addition, biomass harvests and transport should be performed with minimised use of transport fuels and, ideally, zero net release of carbon dioxide to the atmosphere. Therefore, the greatest effect on climate impact reduction will be achieved by plantations that are localised, designed and managed according to commercial principles.

If plantations are established mainly for reasons other than pure biomass production, e.g., phytoremediation to achieve the environmental objectives 'A Non-Toxic Environment' or 'Zero Eutrophication', factors other than commercial interests could guide the location, design and management of plantations. For example, location and design of plantations along rivers (e.g., to reduce nitrate leakage from nearby agricultural fields) will be guided by the topography and landscape, implying that factors such as distance to end-user or optimum harvest conditions might become less important. Nevertheless, the phytoremediation capacity of plantations is commonly strongly linked to biomass production capacity and all factors favouring high biomass yield will also favour phytoremediation capacity. Consequently, phytoremediation capacity of plantations will generally be favoured by the same factors as in pure (commercial) biomass plantations, with the exception that the variety choice for maximised biomass production might differ from the variety choice for phytoremediation purposes.

Biodiversity and environmental issues

During recent years the planting of large areas of fast-growing trees has sparked off much controversy, especially in the areas of the world where most of the expansion of fast-wood plantations is expected to take place (i.e., South America and East Asia). Critics of these plantations of fast-growing trees include environmentalists, who argue that they are causing harm to wildlife, water resources and the soil and decrease biodiversity (Cossalter and Pye-Smith 2003). Indeed, much tree planting in recent decades, especially in the Tropics, has had negative environmental impacts, but the problems of plantation forests are frequently associated with inappropriate location and management; therefore, relatively modest changes in the ways that tree plantations are established and managed could result in greatly improved outcomes for the environment (WWF 2003). For example, compared to natural mixed coniferous forests of the Pacific Northwest, Halpern and Spiess (1995) regarded large poplar plantations to decrease flora diversity in the long term. In contrast, compared to managed coniferous forests and farmland in boreal Sweden, young poplar and willow plantations, especially if not too large in size, have been concluded to increase vascular-plant diversity (Gustafsson 1987, Weih *et al.* 2003, Augustson *et al.* 2006). The proximity of native (deciduous) woodlands is of great importance: birds, insects and even plants have an easier path to spread into the forest plantations if a "natural" forest is situated nearby (Figure 2). Smaller groups of indigenous broad-leaved trees can also be planted in connection with the *Salix* plantation.

Figure 2. If farmland with *Salix* plantations is located in the vicinity of forest land, different animals and plants may more easily spread into the plantations and thus contribute to an increased biodiversity. When the stand is harvested, the adjacent woodlands may act as refuge for many species of animals until the plantation is grown up again. Photo: N.-E. Nordh.

The location of tree plantations within the landscape context exerts a strong influence on their effect on biodiversity: A native wood near the tree plantation will facilitate the migration of birds, insects and plants and, thus, increase biodiversity. If no native woods are present, small groups of native trees can be planted near to the fast-wood plantation. The native woods will serve as retreat area where animals and insects can survive during the periods of clear-cut in the fast-wood plantation. In large plantations, different parcels of the stand can be established and harvested in different years in order to enhance structural diversity and biodiversity. The same goal could be achieved by establishing a large number of smaller plantations, which are harvested in different years. Both alternatives can possibly improve the possibilities for biological control of herbivorous insects, which can be a serious problem in fast-wood plantations (Björkman *et al.* 2004). Mixtures of different species or varieties can be established either by planting them in different blocks across the field or random mixtures within each row (e.g., Aronsson 1995, Volk *et al.* 2004). These mixtures increase structural and functional diversity and contribute to reduce the impact of pests and diseases (Ramstedt 1999, McCracken and Dawson 2001). Finally, a few metres wide strips along the edges of tree plantations could be left without trees to support the development of a rich native flora and fauna. Thus, the location and management of plantations of fast-growing trees should be planned carefully, in order to reduce the risks for environment and utilise at best their potential to improve environmental and landscape quality. For example, intensively managed plantations of fast-growing trees imply the risk of negative effects on the environment in terms of herbicide application, deteriorated soil properties and nutrient leakage. However, when compared to conventional arable crops, the perennial character of the crops used in tree plantations commonly leads to reduced herbicide application (i.e., herbicide treatment is required only during the establishment of the crop; Figure 3; Gustafsson *et al.* 2007).

Figure 3. In older plantations, as the one in this photo, the heavy shading effectively suppresses growth and development of the ground vegetation. Weed control is therefore needed only during the establishment of the plantation.

Further, plantations of fast-growing trees on former arable land often have positive effects on soil properties due to less frequent use of heavy machinery, especially when the use of harvesters is restricted to the period of frozen ground in winter-cold regions. For example, carbon sequestration and water holding capacity were found to increase in formerly arable soils that were planted with fast-growing willow and poplar for 6 to 10 years (Kahle *et al.* 2005). The perennial nature of tree plantations also leads to less nutrient leakage compared to conventional arable crops provided that the rate and timing of fertilisation is adjusted to the nutrient delivery and nutrient holding capacity of the soil in relation to the uptake capacity of the trees (Ericsson *et al.* 1992). This may imply the application of repeated, small fertilisations throughout the growing season according to a scenario following tree growth, i.e., small amounts early and late in the season and larger amounts in mid-summer (Ingestad 1987, Alriksson *et al.* 1997). If tree plantations are managed according to these principles, they are unlikely to endanger the environment by means of groundwater contamination even under the short periods of plant nutrient uptake that are typical under the cool climate of high-latitude regions (Aronsson *et al.* 2000).

In contrast to the potential risks of nutrient leakage from fertilised plantations, plantations of fast-growing trees can offer great possibilities for environmental control at a local scale in terms of, e.g., phytoremediation. Thus, based on the large nutrient quantities taken up by fast-growing trees, the plantations can be used as recipients for municipal wastewater and industrial sludge and simultaneous biomass production (multifunctional biomass plantations, Perttu 1993, Aronsson and Perttu 2001, Labrecque and Teodorescu 2003). A major problem occurs particularly in regions with extended dormant periods during winter, where only very small quantities of nutrients are taken up by plants. This sort of wastewater treatment can therefore be accomplished in winter-cold regions only if the wastewater is stored in ponds or lagoons during the winter period (Rosenqvist *et al.* 1997).

Tree plantations can have positive or negative effects on biodiversity, depending on location, management and previous land use (Cossalter and Pye-Smith 2003) and studies on biodiversity in plantations of fast-growing trees often arrive at contradictory conclusions especially when different kinds of organisms are considered (Hartley 2002). Thus, the landscape context (forest or agricultural, Hanowski *et al.* 1997, Weih *et al.* 2003) along with the land-use type that the plantation replaces (Christian *et al.* 1994) and spatial scale aspects (e.g. size or design of plantation; Christian *et al.* 1994, Berg 2002) influence the impact of establishment of tree plantations on biodiversity. In addition, many animals use multiple habitats and therefore depend on certain habitat combinations (With *et al.* 1997, Law and Dickman 1998) and the diversity of land use types in a given landscape can have large impacts on biodiversity.

Similar to the observations on flora, fauna diversity (birds and mammals) is frequently found to be higher in willow and hybrid poplar stands compared to agricultural croplands (Göransson 1994, Christian *et al.* 1998, Berg 2002). Thus, the more extensive management of tree plantations compared to intensively managed cereal crops can improve habitat quality for many organisms including plants, birds and arachnids (Berg 2002, Blick and Burger 2002, Dhondt *et al.* 2004, Weih *et al.* 2003). In addition, plantations of fast-growing trees appear to have a potential as important habitats for gamebirds (Sage and Robertson 1994).

It hence appears that tree plantations, if not too large in size and if planned creatively, can increase the abundance and diversity of many organisms, particularly in landscape dominated by either conventional agricultural fields or managed coniferous forests, by increasing structural diversity. However, plantations should be avoided close to open habitats of high conservation values such as certain types of wet meadows and buffer zones along streams, because such sites often have a conservation value linked to openness of the habitat (Berg 2002). With the above restrictions in mind, small-scale tree plantations (or sub-divided larger plantations) grown on agricultural land may have the potential to positively affect biodiversity in many farmland regions, where the set-aside of agricultural land from food production suggests the development of alternative uses.

Landscape design and cultural heritage

Plantations of fast-growing trees may already after a few years of growth be up to 6 or 8 m in height and it is important to consider the impact this will have on the landscape at the early planning stages of a plantation of fast-growing trees. Many concerns are raised regarding the impact of plantations of fast-growing trees on the landscape (e.g., Skärbäck and Becht 2005): Will the open agricultural landscape be “darkened” by a new type of forest? How will the new crop be adapted to the traditional field crops of agricultural landscapes? Will we soon experience a total transformation of our ingrained cultural heritage? Studies regarding the effects of plantations of fast-growing trees on visual landscape perception usually arrive at different conclusions, e.g., the more open the landscape is, the larger can the size of the plantations be and particularly small plantations placed in open agricultural landscape can enrich landscape perception; small-scale undulating landscape only “tolerates” small plantations (Rode 2005, Skärbäck and Becht 2005). A general comment

is often that plantations of fast-growing trees are an exciting new feature of the landscape, these plantations can enhance the aesthetic value of landscape by adding variation (e.g., autumn colours) and structure in homogeneous agricultural landscape (Skärbäck and Becht 2005).

If used creatively as part of active landscape analysis and design, plantations of fast-growing trees can greatly improve the visual and recreational values of a landscape (e.g., Enberg 2002, Rode 2005). For example, monotonous structures in blocks of tree plantations can be broken up by edge strips of native herbs and woods, which are flowering and thereby can increase the aesthetic value of the landscape (Rode 2005).

Concerns have also been raised regarding the impact that plantations of fast-growing trees might have on archaeological sites and deposits. However, these plantations will be no more damaging to archaeology than arable cropping or commercial forestry and most critical sites such as very wet profiles are not desirable for the establishment of fast-growing trees even by other (biological) reasons. Particular attention should nevertheless be paid to the potential impact of plantations of fast-growing trees on the conservation of historic, designed landscape and it is important to consider these aspects at the early planning stages of this kind of plantation.

Synergies and conflicts of interest

Plantations of fast-growing trees are economic enterprises in most cases and economic profit arguments (i.e., maximised biomass yield after the shortest possible time) usually guide their location, design and management in the first place. Location, design and management of commercial fast-wood plantations are partly conflicting with the primary interests of nature conservation and landscape design (Table 1). Regarding location of these plantations, no serious conflicts of interest appear to exist between the interests of commercial growers, nature conservationists and landscape designers (Table 2) if plantations are established outside areas of high nature conservation and cultural heritage values. Synergies between commercial and nature conservational interests could be achieved by location of plantations nearby native woods, which favour biodiversity (see above) and also shelter the plantation from extremes in climate (e.g., frost) and, thereby, improve sustainable productivity of the plantation (Weih 2006). No serious conflicts of interests are expected between nature conservation and landscape design principles of shaping and managing tree plantations (Tables 1 & 2). Possibly could synergies be achieved through the establishment of edge habitats consisting of attractive (flowering) plants that have high conservational value for plants and insects?

Commercial willow culture may frequently conflict with the interests of nature conservation and landscape design regarding the design and management of tree plantations. For example, large monoclonal, block-shaped and very fast growing tree stands that are harvested frequently as a whole are desirable from a purely commercial perspective, whereas many small-sized, irregularly shaped stands consisting of several species and/or clones and harvested in different years would be preferred by nature conservationists and landscape designers (Tables 1 & 2).

Table 1. Desirable actions for location, design and management of plantations of fast-growing trees according to purely commercial, environmental (nature conservation) and landscape design principles (after Weih 2006).

	Commercial	Nature conservation	Landscape design
Location	Agricultural land, short transport distances to end user, easy accessibility with heavy machinery	Agricultural land, nearby native woods, not in areas of high nature conservation value and not in landscape dominated by forest	Not in areas of high cultural heritage value and at visually exposed locations where traditional landscape views would be destroyed, preferably in open and homogeneous agricultural landscape, not in areas dominated by forest (to prevent a negative perception of landscape, the total fraction of forested area in a landscape should not exceed 40 - 50%, Wöbse 2003)
Design	Large and block-shaped plantations that can be harvested effectively, homogeneous and highly productive plant material (preferably monoclonal stands) that rapidly generates homogeneous biomass	Small-scale plantations, strips or small groups of native woods in the edges of the plantation, heterogeneous plant material (preferably multi-species or polyclonal stands) including male-sex varieties (insect pollination!)	Small-scale plantations, stripes of native vegetation consisting of attractive species (flowering, autumn colors, etc.)
Management	Effective weeding (chemical) prior to plantation establishment, optimal mineral nutrient fertilisation "according to plant demand" (preferably with sludge or waste water from sewage plant), short cutting cycles, simultaneous harvest of the whole stand	Restrictive application of chemical weeding, not to high nutrient fertilisation "according to plant demand" (to prevent leakage to groundwater), long cutting cycles, different parts of plantation are harvested different years, native edge habitats are left untouched at least during harvest of the tree plantation	No deep ploughing (to prevent disturbance of archeological deposits), native edge habitats are left untouched at least during harvest of the tree plantation

Table 2. Summary of possible conflicts of interest (yes, no) between commercial (C), environmental (nature conservation, N) and landscape design (L) principles with regard to the location, design and management of willow plantations grown on agricultural land (after Weih 2006)

	Location		Design		Management	
	N	L	N	L	N	L
C						
N	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
		no		no		no

Waste-water, sludge and other residues contain plant nutrients and the application of these substances to plantations of fast-growing trees is advantageous from a commercial perspective (Rosenqvist and Ness 2004). If nutrient proportions in the applied solutions are appropriate for plant growth, leakage to ground water can be avoided (Aronsson and Perttu 2001) and no serious conflicts between the different perspectives are expected. However, there are so far no scientific studies on the effects of waste water and sludge applications on biodiversity in plantations of fast-growing trees and there is a potential risk that the application of these substances to tree plantations will have negative impact on biodiversity.

Opinions of Different Stakeholders on *Salix* Culture

Location, design and management of willow short rotation coppice are issues that are relevant not only for central and regional authorities, but also for farmer and home district organisations, various stakeholders, university academics and companies with interests in these or related issues. In order to achieve an overall impression of the relevant conflicts of interest and to evaluate the possibilities to meet these, a simple questionnaire was formulated and sent to representatives of the above mentioned groups during April 2005. The questionnaire consisted of the following seven questions (the original material is found in Weih, 2006).

- 1) Is the term “*Salix* plantation” associated with positive, neutral or negative connotations at your organisation?
- 2) Which positive opportunities do you/your organisation associate with *Salix* plantations on agricultural land?
- 3) Which problems can arise with the plantation of *Salix* on agricultural land?
- 4) Do you have an opinion on where in the landscape *Salix* plantations should be located, and where these plantations should be avoided? Please try to motivate your statement!
- 5) How should *Salix* plantations be designed (regarding, e.g., size of plantation, selection of plant material)? Please try to motivate your statement!
- 6) Should particular management actions (apart from those increasing productivity) be taken in order to increase the environmental benefits of a *Salix* plantation? Which particular management actions should be taken, and why?
- 7) Which additional comments do you want to add?

In total 72 questionnaires were sent out by e-mail and 53 replies had been received until January 2006, which corresponds to a reply rate of 74%. The reply rate varied between the various groups according to the following pattern: central authorities 75%, county administration boards 61%, farmer and home district organisations 75%, bioenergy and landscape design stakeholders 100%, nature conservation organisations 100%, university professionals 81% and companies 67%. The following chapters briefly summarise the responses from the various groups.

Central authorities

The **Swedish Energy Agency** (*Energimyndigheten*) has a positive attitude towards *Salix* plantations on agricultural land, because the plantations contribute to renewable energy and *Salix* culture is associated with soil carbon sequestration, reduced nutrient leakage (compared to the culture of cereals), uptake of cadmium and favourable environment for some animals and plants. The greatest problems can arise, according to this authority, if plantations are poorly located and disturb the landscape perception, in particular by reducing the proportion of "open landscape".

Considering management, the authority points to the problems regarding soil cadmium: varieties with a great capacity to take up cadmium can be used to remedy soils, but may cause problems in handling of the ashes. It is also pointed out that the phytoremediation potential of *Salix* culture should be utilised as much as possible. An interesting final comment was the strong opinion of the authority that the positive side effects of *Salix* plantations on the environment should be made public much better, since in the public discussion of this issue usually only the negative aspects and the problems of *Salix* culture are pointed out. However, the stated problems and misgivings (e.g., 'How bad would it be if we started planting *Salix* in the National Parks?') are in many cases irrelevant in the context of practical *Salix* culture.

For the **Swedish National Heritage Board** (*Riksantikvarieämbetet*) have *Salix* plantations on agricultural land a negative connotation, mainly because these new cropping systems will lead to "a new landscape that can screen off the views that have been open for centuries or even millennia" and "stump removal...often requires deep ploughing, which can damage the soil layers containing archaeological subjects, which are rarely registered". A positive effect may be that "*Salix* plantations can be a source of income in addition to the usual farming, and thus contribute to maintain the character of a living agricultural landscape...". *Salix* plantations should however not be established in areas that are of national interest for heritage protection, or other valuable cultural sites, such as in "traditional agricultural fields next to older rural housing and close to the tombs of ancient monuments or rune stones." Important regarding the location and design of plantations is that the plantations are established so that "an area does not become permanently shielded, i.e., that from a housing some open views are always available". In addition, it would be preferable to use "*Salix* varieties that are similar to grain habit" and "low-growing plantations, preferably lower than c. 2 m in height". The recommendation is in any case, that consultations with county administration boards, in particular their

cultural heritage units, should be done in the planning of any *Salix* plantation on agricultural land.

The **Swedish Board of Agriculture** (*Jordbruksverket*) has a neutral to positive view on *Salix* agriculture, which is seen as a form of agriculture producing "raw material among all other products that are possible to cultivate on agricultural land." Among the positive possibilities is mentioned that these plantations may be an alternative land use to fallow land, that they imply "less work due to the perennial character of the crop", that "the produced goods can be used for energy", and the great potential for enhanced productivity with new varieties of *Salix*. Regarding potential problems, the authority points out mainly cultivation technique issues, however, without going into any detail. Regarding the location of *Salix* plantations it is mentioned that the "Establishment of *Salix* plantations can, in some cases, damage the landscape perception, impact on the cultural heritage character of landscape as a whole and imply loss of biodiversity. Whether this is the case or not is determined through consultation in accordance with Chapter 12, Section 6, of environmental legislation (*miljöbalken*)". Moreover, when *Salix* plantations are planned, the arrangement of housing in the landscape should be taken into consideration, as well as opinions of "the residents of the neighbourhood". Also, plantations should be planted only at a distance to housing areas. Regarding the design and management of plantations, reference is made to "organizations that are closer to *Salix* cultivation practice."

The **Swedish Forest Agency** (*Skogsstyrelsen*) did not respond to the questionnaire.

County administration boards (*Länsstyrelser*)⁵

Agricultural units of the county administration boards (7 responses) were mostly neutral in their general attitude towards *Salix* plantations, with two negative and one positive response. Two agricultural units did not see any positive opportunities with the cultivation of *Salix*. Other responses included an opportunity to increase profitability of the individual farm business, no requirements on own investments in machinery since all the necessary services can be bought in, more jobs in plant breeding and marketing business, the production of renewable energy in the county (greater self-sufficiency) and thus less dependency on imported fossil fuels, and that agricultural land is kept in production. The main problems are seen in the strong impact of *Salix* plantations on the landscape (plantations make landscape "ugly" landscape; conflicts with cultural heritage interests) and that *Salix* plantations often appear not "sufficient" profitable. Agricultural units also pointed out problems with drainage systems, which can be destroyed by tree roots. Regarding the location of *Salix* plantations it was, for example, frequently stated that plantations should be "put in another county" (because within their county is good supply of forestry residues), planted on less profitable arable land and in the edges of open agricultural landscape, as well as planned in such a way that sensitive nature conservation and cultural sites are not disturbed. With respect to the design and management of plantations, the surveyed agricultural units had no views and referred to the farmers. For half of the **nature conservation units** at county administrative boards (6 answers) is the term "Salix plantations" associated with both positive and

⁵ Questionnaires have only been sent out in areas where *Salix* plantations are found.

negative attitudes (neutral), while two of the surveyed units refrained from opinion ("no time to respond") and one was positive. Among the positive opportunities they see that *Salix* plantations "normally do not conflict with environmental values" and that they "can increase biodiversity (especially in comparison with spruce plantations on agricultural land)". They also pointed out positive opportunities for outdoor activities, especially if the plantations are supplied with rambling paths. The biggest problem is considered to be improperly located plantations that disrupt the landscape perception and valuable nature protection areas. Therefore, the nature conservation units have an opinion regarding the location of *Salix* plantations: they should not be located in the old cultural landscape with a large proportion of grassland and pasture, and not so that they are destroying the countryside, especially in the "old agricultural landscape". Instead, the plantations should be located among large homogeneous agricultural fields of traditional crops to increase the variation in the landscape. Most nature conservation units had no opinion on the design and management of plantations. In one response, however, a "high species diversity" (increased biodiversity) is desired, and that not all plantations in an area are harvested at the same time.

Most negative (67%) with regard to the term "*Salix* plantation" were the **cultural heritage units** of the county administration boards (6 replies), with only one positive response and one response "no time to respond." As a positive opportunity is seen that *Salix* plantations can create a livelihood for the farmers, thereby helping to maintain or revive a living countryside. Furthermore, these plantations can, according to one of the answers, contribute to the work towards the sustainable society by promoting the transition to renewable energy. Among the biggest problems are mentioned;

- (1) "ancient landscape lines are destroyed, i.e., those lines likely to have existed and been planned already from the start of the region's colonisation";
- (2) plantations alter the landscape so that "we do not feel at home in their immediate environment";
- (3) "after a shift to *Salix* cultivation, it is difficult to go back to the cultivation of cereals, due to the extensive tree root systems of *Salix*";
- (4) "conflicts with ancient monuments, both visible and those that we know are hidden beneath the ground and affected by the root system";
- (5) landscape of *Salix* plantations is perceived as "overgrown"(negatively) and "the transition from traditional agricultural crops to forest [is seen] as a serious threat to the cultural landscape that is characteristic of the county".

Regarding the location of plantations, areas "in or near the valuable cultural sites" should be avoided, such as areas "where high cultural values of the traditional landscape have been identified" and areas "in the open landscape nearby the villages, which have a long tradition of open agricultural landscape". One response indicated that *Salix* plantations only should be located "in connection with forest or forest land." With respect to the design and management of plantations also most of the cultural heritage units had no opinion. In a response, it is felt, however, that "small and well-positioned plantations are preferable".

Municipalities

Responses have been received from the municipalities (nature or environmental units) in Köping, Uppsala, Örebro and Västerås. The environmental protection unit in Västerås considers that it has not directly to do with the issue and did not reply to the questionnaire. The other municipalities had a neutral (2) or positive view of *Salix* plantation on agricultural land. As a positive opportunity with *Salix* plantations was mentioned "sustainable energy", "variation in agricultural landscape", "favourable to the bird life" and that *Salix* plantation is a good option for agricultural land "to be taken out of production because of the surplus of cereals". Problems are seen especially in the context of damage to drainage systems (in particular if one, after a few years, wants to switch to grain production again), smell at sludge spreading across *Salix* plantations, accidents with animals using the plantations, leakage of nutrients, altered landscape perception and that the natural and cultural environment can be damaged at the wrong location of plantations. "Old landscape" and "the traditional flat type agricultural landscape" should therefore not be planted with *Salix*. In contrast, "traditional agricultural land" as well as "land in connection with forest" may be planted with *Salix* "to create more variety in the landscape. The design of plantations should take into account a maximum plantation size of 10 ha per plot and the use of "indigenous species" in the culture. Regarding the management harvests should be carried out at different times in the different parts (or parcels) of the plantation. In addition, plantations should be fertilized with urban sludge and waste water, "so we get a good recycling of these products". To prevent nutrient leaching, "the fertilizer scheme needs to be adapted to the crop absorption capacity" at different seasons and growth stages of the *Salix* plantation.

Farmer and home district organisations

The Federation of Swedish Farmers (*Lantbrukarnas Riksförbund, LRF*) sees *Salix* plantations on agricultural land as a positive opportunity; especially as "an alternative for marginal farmland" (this probably means infertile arable land). Major problems are seen by means of the risk of "crop failure" and that "*Salix* grows into and distorts the drainage system".

The Swedish Ecological Farmers (*Ekologiska Lantbrukarna*), which is a federation of organic farmers, have a neutral view on *Salix* culture and see positive opportunities associated with the production of renewable energy on arable land and "the maintenance of active farms in rural areas". Problems can arise since the "net production of energy can be small and then the energy value might be questioned" (i.e., the energy efficiency must be assessed). In addition, the quality of arable land can be harmed in the short term, when the roots penetrate into the drainage system and in the long term, if urban sludge and other residues from society should be placed on arable land with *Salix* plantations. The location of the plantations should be done so that not "valuable nature conservation, cultural heritage or agricultural areas disappear" and preferably should the plantations should be located "where they contribute to a change in an otherwise monotonous landscape". With respect to the design of plantations, they should consist of a number of different varieties to increase cropping reliability and not be too large. The management should be done under organic farming methods.

The **KRAV association**, which is a key player in the organic market in Sweden and develops organic standards, did not respond to the inquiry as the association believes itself to be a pure certifying organisation not having any reason to discuss the issue of *Salix* plantations on agricultural land.

For **The Swedish Local Heritage Federation** (*Sveriges Hembygdsförbund*), the term *Salix* plantation has "broadly negative connotation". However, the federation is also aware of some positive opportunities, e.g., that biomass from *Salix* plantations can be an alternative to fossil fuels (however, the federation would prefer other energy crops such as energy grass, straw, etc.) and that *Salix* culture may contribute to maintenance and development of rural areas. From the cultural heritage perspective the federation sees no positive opportunities associated with willow plantations. Major problems are pointed out in that the plantations "affect the spatial aesthetic perception of the landscape generally, but above all suffer the cultural and historical values when traditional structures and connections are broken". Another point of view is that the "root systems affect cultural ground layers" and drainage systems. Prior to any decision regarding the location of plantations, one must "in each case also make use of antiquarian skills". In addition, the "knowledge of the historic landscape must be a basis for the corresponding discussions". With regard to the design of plantations should "varieties with different heights and character" and "low-growing varieties" be preferred, edge habitats "can be good even from a cultural heritage perspective". Regarding the management, one should "be careful with heavy machinery that affects soil structure and cultural ground layers".

Bioenergy and landscape design stakeholders

The terms *Salix* plantation and *Salix* energy forestry have generally positive connotation for the Swedish bioenergy association **Svebio**, but the organisation would prefer terms such as "energy from agricultural land", "energy crops" or "agricultural fuel" to delineate against biomass from forest land. Among the positive possibilities are seen high energy value (biomass tonnes) per hectare achieved with relatively low levels of supporting actions and the possibility to take care of nitrogen in waste water in a cost-effective manner. The organisation also refers to a positive impact on the landscape, such as "protection zones" and feed for livestock species, wind protection and less use of fertilisers and pesticides compared to "other crops". The only problem with the cultivation of *Salix*, as Svebio can see, is "the local change in the landscape, i.e., how the local residents perceive their environment". However, it is pointed out that the effect on landscape must be valued "in relation to how the land would otherwise have been used" and that "the landscape is not unchangeable. It is natural that every era has its own way to make use of natural resources, which in turn creates the landscape". Regarding the location and design of plantations, Svebio believes that these are primarily matters for the individual grower and "We believe it is both difficult and inappropriate to regulate this by guidelines from the authorities". If one can influence the location of plantations, one should "refrain from the plantation where it creates the most irritation among neighbours". With regard to the management it is pointed out that "the environmental benefit is in the first place in that it one can grow bioenergy to

replace fossil fuels and this environmental benefit increases with increased energy production" and that "unnecessary restrictions which limit energy cropping should therefore be avoided". For fertilisation and pesticides should "the same rules apply as for agriculture in general".

Even for the **Swedish Association of Architects** (*Akademien för Landskapsarkitektur*) the term *Salix* energy plantations has a positive connotation and is mainly associated with "sustainable energy production" and "reversible land use". Problems mentioned in connection with the cultivation of *Salix* are that "the typical character of lowland agricultural landscape may be adversely affected", "the terrific views may disappear" and "diverse traditional landscape becomes overgrown with bushes and ugly". Location should preferably take place "in less fertile sites", "in the valley" and "in wetlands", but it should be avoided to plant willows all way "around lowland lakes". Even woodlands near settlements and sites "of the sort overgrown pastures and meadows where the alternative is hopeless dense spruce woods" are considered interesting for the planting of willow energy crops. Regarding the design of plantations should "the size be adapted to the landscape context" and the questions are asked: "Why only species of willow? Why not hazel and other species?". Overall, the plantations should not be too large and "they have to be crossed by paths and roads". Regarding the management the opportunities for the use of *Salix* plantations "for hiking to expand the land available for outdoor activities" are pointed out, as well as the possibilities for phytoremediation of waste water. A final comment is that the goal of the investigation "should be among the tasks for professionals in landscape planning".

Nature conservation organisations

Among the surveyed organizations has the term *Salix* energy plantation a neutral or positive connotation.

The **World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)** sees as positive opportunities the "diversification of large monotonous lowland landscape, reduced nutrient leakage to groundwater, protection for birds and wildlife, pollen / nectar source for bees and bumble bees". A potential problem might be that crops can interfere with the landscape in "sensitive" areas (regarding cultural and environmental values), and this is why willow plantations should be avoided in these areas. In contrast, plantations should with advantage be "placed along the rivers to reduce nutrient leaching". With respect to the design of plantations it is pointed out that "non-GMO varieties and varieties that do not hybridize with wild species" should be used in the plantations.

For the **Swedish Society for Nature Conservation** (*Svenska Naturskyddsföreningen, SNF*) the culture of *Salix* is associated with a number of positive opportunities, such as increasing the share of renewable energy, increased diversity in monotonous lowland arable landscape, new markets for agriculture and thus an opportunity to maintain an active farming in the whole of Sweden, and to clean soil from heavy metals. A major problem related to *Salix* energy plantations is that "the energy outcome will not be sufficient". In that context it is pointed out that "*Salix* energy plantations may not always be the best climate policy - especially

if the cultivation is done with high use of fertilizers and chemical pesticides". Another problem is, according to the organisation, that the "landscape of high natural and cultural values is replaced with plantations of *Salix*". As for the location of plantations it is indicated that "*Salix* energy plantations should primarily be used to increase the variety in monotonous landscape such as plains". It is noted that we "currently lack sufficient knowledge of how *Salix* plantations impact on the natural and cultural values of landscape", and that it is important to "not destroy agricultural landscape with high natural and cultural values". Regarding management of plantations the organisation believes that "the same environmental standards should be set to *Salix* energy plantations as on other crops" and that "organic production of *Salix* should reward".

Sweden's Ornithological Society (*Sveriges Ornitologiska Förening, SOF*) sees a positive opportunity by means of an increase in "variation in a biological poor agricultural landscape (especially in large-scale agriculture)". As the biggest problem, it is felt that large areas of great interest for birds are occupied by *Salix* energy plantations. Therefore, these plantations should not be established in wetlands. Regarding the design of the plantations, maximised "variation" is desired. In addition, the organisation notes that conflicts with *Salix* energy plantations in the context of bird protection so far have not appeared and, therefore, are not to be expected.

The **Swedish Hunters Association** (*Svenska Jägareförbundet*) recognizes positive opportunities of *Salix* plantations in terms of "food and shelter to wildlife and variation in the agricultural landscape". The association sees "no immediate problems" with the culture of *Salix*, but the plantations should be located "scattered in the landscape" and "in connection with lakes or rivers". Regarding the design of plantations "crops that are attractive to game" are desired.

University professionals

Total 11 scientists representing different subjects and having been working on issues related to *Salix* cultivation have responded to the survey. For 6 of these researchers, the term *Salix* energy plantation has positive connotation, while 5 of these indicate "neutral" and 1 indicates "negative" connotation.

Landscape design, SLU, Uppsala and Alnarp (C. Florgård, E. Skärbäck): Skärbeck refers to Skärbäck and Becht (2005), a paper which has been discussed above. As positive opportunities are otherwise mentioned the treatment of waste water, use of plantations as shelters, fixation of dust along the roads, "interesting variations in the landscape" and to "keep farmland in cultivation". A problem with these plantations might be profound effects on the "character of landscape" (e.g., views might be blocked). Location of plantations can be done "in many places, through the use of harvests in different years". However, one should "be careful with willow plantations where they might interfere with an attractive landscape for outdoor activities". Regarding the design and management of plantations the participating researchers saw no reason for any restrictions in remote areas, but in the areas "where people go and stay, the plantations must be designed by professional landscape designers".

Physical Geography and Ecosystem Analysis, University of Lund (A. Lindroth):

The following positive opportunities are associated with *Salix* plantations on agricultural land:

- (1) mitigate climate change by replacing fossil fuel,
- (2) increased biodiversity in the agricultural landscape,
- (3) reduced nitrogen leaching and
- (4) greater variation in the landscape (if plantations are located "right"). Problems may arise with respect to the "poor management that generates low yields and negative attitudes" and the "people's demands for open landscape perception", which may create "problems in the public acceptance".

The location of plantations should avoid the creation of "coherent huge areas of plantations" and "dense curtains along the roads". Another view was that we should "change people's perception of *Salix* energy plantations" and "to offer model calculations of how organizations...could minimize their net carbon dioxide emissions, for example, through the plantation of X ha energy crops".

Conservation Biology and the Swedish Biodiversity Centre, SLU and Uppsala University, Uppsala (L. Gustafsson, Å Berg):

As positive opportunities with *Salix* energy plantations are mentioned "increased habitat variation/number of species at landscape level" and "favourable for birds, insects and certain plants," problems are seen by means of "leaching of nitrogen, pesticides", and a wrong location nearby "valuable open environments such as shoreline meadows or along rivers and other wetlands". Plantations should be localized where "the landscape view is affected in a positive direction, for example, to break up large monotonous plains", but not close to valuable open environments and "in scattered landscape with plenty of woods". The design "should be adapted to the landscape degree of heterogeneity", i.e., "in a heterogeneous and small-scale landscape - small plantations; in a large-scale and homogenous landscape (such as plains) - larger plantations". In addition, the edges of plantations should be planted with various species of trees and shrubs, or "a rich weed flora". With regard to the management it is proposed to allow "a portion of the plantation to grow up free and grow old". Other observations are that "*Salix* plantations should be encouraged at appropriate locations" and "impact assessment studies of plantations near valuable nature/culture conservation areas should be done".

Centre for sustainable agriculture, SLU, Uppsala (U. Geber):

The term *Salix* plantation clearly has a negative connotation, but some positive opportunities are noted in connection with the "purification of nutritious water, local energy production and transport fuels". As the biggest problems it is claimed the "massive use of non-renewable energy sources in the production and processing of biomass" and that the plantations could imply the "disruption of homogenous landscape". Management actions favouring functions other than the purely production oriented should be considered

to a large extent, for example, measures in favour of "the generation of biodiversity" and "purification of nutritious water".

Insect ecology, SLU, Uppsala (C. Björkman):

Among the positive opportunities regarding *Salix* plantations it is mentioned "a break in a flat, monotonous landscape" and that the plantations "could possibly favour beneficial insects". Problems are seen in the context of frequently poor economy for the grower. Regarding the location of plantations, a response was: "Since it is unclear how the plantations affect environmental values such as biodiversity, I think it is good if plantations are placed in as many ways as possible (or rather in a varied but controlled way) across the landscape, in order to enable researchers to explore where the plantations (a) are generating the utmost benefit, (b) are at the greatest risk to be damaged, etc.". With respect to the design of plantations suggests Björkman that "introduction of other plants in or around *Salix* plantations, such as different types of flowering plants,... would be likely to contribute to increased biodiversity and possibly also the control of various pests".

Plant pathology, SLU, Uppsala (M. Ramstedt):

Positive opportunities in connection with *Salix* plantation are seen in terms of "long-term security" for the farmer if he signs a supply agreement and "freedom of choice to change cropping" (as opposed to spruce plantations). Problems may arise in relation to diseases, especially stem attacking bacteria and fungi: "Stem attacks combined with frost sensitivity can kill an entire plantation". *Salix* energy plantations should therefore be avoided at "frost exposed positions, locations to which the cold air flows and is captured at cold nights". The design of plantations should consider that the *Salix* variety "you think is best today may not be the best variety tomorrow, or in other circumstances" and that "the risk of disease [is] greater in large monoclonal stands". It is therefore important to use several varieties to increase cropping reliability. The management should take into account that "spraying in different forms for diseases and insects should not be done, both for environmental and for economic reasons".

Soil science, SLU, Uppsala (S. Ledin):

Regarding the positive opportunities a comparison with solar cells is noted "The process of photosynthesis provides an excellent opportunity to capture and store energy from the sun...and compared with solar cells, the plant can reproduce itself. It is thus cheap to establish plant 'solar panels' across large areas... including agricultural land. Even if solar cells are 15 times more energy efficient per unit area are *Salix* energy plantations a much better alternative due to, among other things, energy storage facilities built in the plant". In addition, it is noted that "litter decomposition in *Salix* plantations leads to more organic matter in soil and vibrant soil biological activity" compared to other crops, and thus probably greater biodiversity. The main problem with *Salix* plantations is related to "the attitudes of people", but also the fact that "drainage systems in agricultural soils can be destroyed by tree roots" can create problems.

Bioenergy, SLU, Uppsala (T. Johansson): Positive opportunities exist as the "unused arable land" can be used for biomass production. The main problem is that the landscape is changed by *Salix* plantations, therefore should plantations be located so that "the original landscape view is obscured as little as possible". For that reason, the plantations should not be "too large". Rapidly growing and frost tolerant varieties should be used "to justify a rational land use". It is called for "proper information of some kind to the general public, preferably in the form of easy-to-read display units that car travellers can read during their ride".

Short rotation forestry, SLU, Uppsala (T. Verwijst): As important positive opportunities it is invoked the production of domestic energy in an environmentally sound manner, thereby reducing dependence on fossil fuels, and the creation of work opportunities and thus an opportunity to "maintain the agricultural landscape" in Sweden. Major problems with *Salix* energy plantations on agricultural land are related to the "conflict of interest between different sections of society" and "agronomic/logistical problems". Location of plantations in the landscape should be "appropriate" and so that ground and surface water quality is affected positively. The design of plantations should be "diverse in many respects."

Biomass technology, SLU, Umeå (H. Örberg): "A contribution to the fuel supply for heating, combined heat and power" and "an alternative to non-profitable cereal cropping in the districts of Götaland and Svealand" are listed as positive opportunities with *Salix* plantations. Problems are seen most in connection with the fear that the open landscape "is turned ugly", especially in "regions with little agricultural land". Therefore desired locations for plantations are "where the landscape is monotonous", but not "in woodlands and throughout northern Sweden". Suggestion: "To harvest after only 3 years instead of four would, in certain situations, reduce the dominance of the plantations in the landscape".

Companies

The company **Lantmännen Agroenergi AB** is part of the Swedish Lantmännen company. Lantmännen is a member-owned economic association with 44000 members throughout Sweden; the majority of members are farmers. As the only player on the Swedish market, the company is working with the planting and sale of plant material (*Salix*), harvesting and sale of *Salix*-chips, sharing of sludge to *Salix* plantations and development of machinery and systems for planting, cultivation, harvesting and transport to the end user (heat and power plants). Obviously, the company has a positive view of *Salix* energy plantations on agricultural land and lists as the positive opportunities "an efficient crop to make money, even for the farmer", "increased land use competition" and the "increasing number of species (crops) in the agricultural landscape". The biggest problem with *Salix* plantations is, according to the company, poor yield due to poor management and poor soil preparation before planting. With respect to the design of plantations the company prefers large stands (greater than 10 ha) and indicates that the plantations less than 2 ha are difficult to harvest. In general, the company is very negative towards variety mixtures (due to a high risk

of non-homogeneous stands, particularly in older plantations), but does not principally rule out the possibility of "6 lines of one variety and 6 lines of a different variety". As environmental management beyond purely production oriented management the company mentions "fertilisation with the sludge" and "that the plantation grows well in order to replace as much as possible of fossil fuels".

The company **Ena Energi AB** is 100% owned by AB Enköpings Värmeverk, which in turn is owned by Västerås municipality. Heat and electricity are produced by using environmentally friendly biofuels, among them a large part *Salix*-chips from biomass plantations that partly have been established on contracted farmland by the company itself. The term *Salix* plantation has a positive connotation for the company, which can see a number of positive opportunities associated with the cultivation of *Salix*: (1) "biomass from *Salix* plantations is used only for energy" and is not a waste product (as forest residuals), which means it can to some extent be harvested as needed; (2) *Salix* plantations "provide an additional opportunity to use the land for agriculture"; (3) "*Salix* plantations are an opportunity to create 'curtains' in the landscape and can change a static landscape" (reference to Enberg, 2002); and (4) possibility to heavy metal uptake from polluted soils and reduced nitrogen leaching into rivers and lakes. Potential problems are seen only with respect to the aesthetics of landscape, and the company believes that landscape aspects and proximity to consumers should govern the location of plantations. As environmentally positive management actions the fertilisation with sludge and ashes is mentioned.

Also for **Vattenfall AB**, the term *Salix* energy plantation has a positive connotation. As positive opportunities with *Salix* plantations is pointed out: "reliable supply", "vicinity", "environmental" and "positive political signals". As the major problems associated with *Salix* plantations the company mentions "profitability" and "location" (i.e. the need for short transport distances for chips to make *Salix* energy plantations a profitable business). The location of plantations should be mainly driven by short transport distances. The design and management of plantations should be guided by an analysis of the whole production chain (life-cycle-analysis, LCA). Small plantations may work well if we can find a sufficient number of farmers who want to cooperate; otherwise large plantations are to be preferred. The company does not own any *Salix* plantations, but indicates that a corresponding strategy is "under development" and plantations under Vattenfalls responsibility may soon become a reality. The company representative stressed, however, that the whole production chain must first be analyzed economically and all players must be heard, so that systems can be developed effectively from the start.

The company **Sydkraft Värme Syd AB** is part of the E.ON group and indicated that it is not carrying out any cultivation of *Salix* and also that the company is a very small user of *Salix* biomass. The biggest problem is seen in that "*Salix* biomass has characteristics that, from our perspective, create technical difficulties in the combustion process". It is also considered as a problem that chips are "difficult to store because they have a best-before date". The company, therefore, refrained from answering the questionnaire.

Conflicts of Interest and the Possibilities to Meet These

The responses from the questionnaire give the impression that the major conflicts of interest between the commercial, environmental and landscape design perspectives are linked to location issues. In the case of the design and management of plantations, respondents frequently referred to farmers or "experts", and respondents to the survey, therefore, gave no clear impression of the potential conflicts of interests with regard to these aspects. However, many of the concerns and expectations towards *Salix* plantations, which were expressed in the responses, are unwarranted for purely agronomic or economic reasons. For example, low-fertile sites (such as lean meadows and pastures) and wetlands are not suitable for cultivation of *Salix*. To break up a *Salix* plantation for replacing it with a different crop, no deep-ploughing is needed to remove the stumps. Thus, according to Swedish and international experience with *Salix* plantations, it is most often enough with ordinary ploughing (20 cm). Heavy machinery is not used more widely for *Salix* cultivation than is the case for conventional cropping of, e.g., cereals. The *Salix* harvester is not heavier than a combine harvester and needed only every three to five years. Weed control agents are used to a much lesser extent (only in connection with the planting) compared with the conventional agriculture of annual crops. *Salix* plantations are less intensively fertilised compared to many other field crops. In addition, the roots of perennial crops, e.g. *Salix*, are active for a longer period of the year, compared with annual crops, and thus counteract the risk of nutrient leakage.

Representatives of the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency see the risk of pollen spreading from *Salix* plantations to native species of *Salix* and that exotic genes are spread into the native flora (T. Nilsson, pers. comm.). In fact, for willow, the varieties of wicker, which are planted in biomass plantations, are often closely related to varieties that much earlier (i.e., in the 1700s) were brought to Sweden for purposes other than biomass plantations (such as material for baskets and other gear used in agriculture, Bergendorff and Emanuelsson, 1982), but there are no reports that those varieties would have hybridized with natural species of *Salix* to any significant degree. Rapidly growing tree species (*Salix*, *Populus*) are generally characterised by abundant seed formation that nevertheless rarely gives rise to new plants (Figure 4). That is why we see very rarely seedlings in plantations of *Salix* or in their vicinity, despite the flowering has been abundant and has given rise to a large amount of seeds. Therefore, the risk of spread of exotic genes from *Salix* energy plantations is probably relatively small.

This is not to say that the culture of fast-growing deciduous trees on agricultural land has no difficulty. For example, there are - compared to annual field crops - disadvantages associated with the deeper root systems that may adversely affect drainage systems. Similarly, cultural heritage subjects hidden in the ground may be injured by tree roots in the same way as in planted woodlands.

In the public debate the starting point is often that *Salix* plantations are ugly and destroy the landscape perception, and the location is the most controversial aspect. The literature review shows, however, that thoughtful design and management in many cases could result in commercial plantations that are acceptable from both the landscape and cultural heritage perspectives. If we design and manage plantations in an appropriate manner that promotes the environmental and cultural aspects as well as attractiveness to the public (see Enberg 2002), the location problems should become less critical. A key to meet many conflicts of interest, apparent or real, is thus to improve communication between different interest groups and involved authorities. Improved communication and dissemination of information may also help to both highlight the positive aspects of *Salix* culture and respond to concerns which, according to the respondents to the survey, are held by some authorities and interest groups.

Figure 4. *Salix* is dioecious, i.e., some plants have only female flowers and others only male flowers. Most commercial *Salix* varieties are hybrids that flower much earlier than the native *Salix* species, which provides a natural barrier to hybridization between them. Photo: P. Aronsson.

Various authorities' varying views on *Salix* plantations means that information about the rules for the establishment and management of these plantations is not always clear and consistent, which greatly complicates the decision-making of farmers who are considering to plant *Salix*. Also this deficiency should be curable with improved coordination between authorities.

The literature review showed that the most serious conflicts are expected between the commercial needs for successful *Salix* culture on one hand and environmental and landscape design desirables on the other hand (see Tables 1 & 2). In order to provide maximum biomass yield and to enable efficient harvests, commercial plantations should be square-shaped and composed of homogeneous and highly productive plant material. In contrast, small-scale plantations of diverse plant material, adjusted to the morphology of landscape and with small scattered groups of native tree species, would be preferable from the environmental and/or landscape design perspectives. These differing perspectives are not entirely incompatible. Different varieties, preferably of different gender and morphology, can be planted in the same stand, but

divided into 10 to 15 m wide "strips", each with its own variety. This should enable efficient harvests and such a design is possible even for commercial growers (G. Melin, Lantmännen Agroenergi AB, pers. comm.). The Swedish *Salix* breeder has both male and female in supply, but noted that customers almost never ask for the gender of varieties (S. Larsson, Lantmännen Agroenergi AB, pers. comm.). This shows that awareness of the possibilities for biodiversity by using varieties of different gender is low among growers and that this uncontroversial opportunity to increase biodiversity is not utilized. With a greater variety of energy crops available in the future may also mixed stands of different energy crops (e.g., willows, poplars, cereals), organised in "strips" as described above, provide much greater landscape- and biodiversity compared with today's biomass plantations in Sweden, which are almost exclusively of *Salix*. For example, in the Swedish climate, poplar is grown best at longer cutting cycles compared to willow (12-15 years, Karacic *et al.*, 2003), which would promote biodiversity, but reduce the temporal variation since stands are harvested less frequently. In addition, poplar grows higher and obstructs views more than *Salix*, which could have positive or negative impact on landscape perception, depending on the context. An adjustment of plantation design to landscape morphology could be achieved with the help of native trees planted in connection with the square-shaped *Salix* stands. In addition, nearby situated plantations could be established and harvested in different years to increase variation in the landscape.

These and similar measures to raise the environmental and landscape values are well known for a fairly long time (e.g., Aronsson, 1995). Yet it is rare that these measures are used in the practice of *Salix* plantations and the positive opportunities for biodiversity and landscape are today hardly utilized. An important reason for this is probably that the design and management of *Salix* plantations is planned solely by entrepreneurs (i.e., commercial growers, in consultation with companies such as Lantmännen Agroenergi AB), while the rest of society (including government) almost exclusively is interested in questions regarding location of plantations and often sees little or no positive opportunities with these plantations except in the climate debate (see the responses to the survey). In addition, there seems to be very little communication between *Salix* entrepreneurs and environmental/landscape/cultural heritage stakeholders. A consequence of this is that plantations either are both designed and operated in accordance with purely commercial principles or are not realised at all. Better knowledge of *Salix* for the relevant authorities and other stakeholders as well as improved communication could thus contribute to better take advantage of the positive opportunities with *Salix* plantations on agricultural land. It is possible that some form of financial compensation to farmers to offset the reduced income caused by the consideration of environmental/landscape aspects, could stimulate the growers' interest in environmentally sound plantations. However, it is not inconceivable that increased environmental requirements (regulation) from the authorities would discourage the establishment of *Salix* energy plantations. Certification for environmentally sound production is perhaps a good option, but currently we lack functional certification systems that are applicable for *Salix* plantations on agricultural land⁶. Good options are Growers' manuals, guidelines or recommendations stressing the importance of environmentally sound farming, and giving practical advice on how plantations should be located, designed

⁶After the successful establishment of *Salix* plantations, which usually requires chemical weed control, a *Salix* stand might indeed comply with the rules of organic farming if no commercial fertilizers are applied.

and managed in order to best take advantage of the positive opportunities for environment and landscape while being economically viable. These recommendations should be easily available to farmers, authorities and the public.

Economic sound production of biomass, increased biodiversity or terrific landscape views – or a combination of these?

Plantations of fast-growing trees on agricultural land can be planned and established for different purposes, e.g., the production of biomass for energy, the phytoremediation of contaminated soils and the cleaning of waste water (Aronsson and Perttu 2001, Verwijst 2001). At the planning and establishment of a culture of fast-growing trees the plantation purpose should be clearly formulated, as this affects the location, design and management of the plantation. Although different objectives can be reconciled to some extent, these often require trade-offs and priorities. If one intends to, for example, achieve maximum profitability in the plantation, the use of fast-growing species on fertile land is required and it would not be a good idea to grow "hazel and other species" (e.g. above, the response from the Swedish Association of Architects), or "low-growing plantations" (e.g. above, the response from the Swedish National Heritage Board). For maximum profitability, plantation also cannot be "an option for marginal farmland" (i.e., poor arable land, e.g. above, the response from the Federation of Swedish Farmers). If, however, priority should be given to the cultural heritage and landscape values of a planned *Salix* plantation, one has most likely to compromise the expected profitability, which probably most farmers cannot afford. The challenge is to create win-win combinations between profitable farming on one hand and the environmental/landscape interests on the other hand. The literature review has shown that there is a potential for synergies between the three perspectives (commercial, environmental, landscape), a potential that should be exploited, but this requires that all parties have a genuine interest in an active dialogue based on the facts.

A question of almost political dimension is how hard we should push the intensification of *Salix* agriculture to effectively replace fossil fuels before the environmental benefits in the form of positive climate impacts are being lost through, *inter alia*, loss of biodiversity. It is conceivable that on the one hand dedicated land for intensive farming of biofuels, without environmental considerations and with high returns as the only objective, and on the other hand dedicated areas for purely environmental purposes where no biofuel production is conducted. Alternatively, existing plantations can be managed as environmentally sound as possible. The issue is clearly outside the mandate of this report, but the findings indicate that the issue may remain of less importance as long as we do not better take advantage of the available possibilities to increase the environmental (cf. biodiversity) and landscape value of *Salix* plantations. The overall objective should be to promote a broad variety of plantations with different purposes and therefore different designs (including various combinations of crops), management strategies and sizes. It is this sort of variation that could create the conditions for different organisms to thrive in an agricultural landscape that may also provide visual variety especially in homogenous agricultural landscape. This kind of variation is probably achieved in

the most efficient way by disseminating information on the positive opportunities associated with *Salix* plantations, rather than by means of more regulations from the authorities. Because we still know rather little about how different types of tree plantations are affecting plants and animals, would a broad variety of plantations with different purposes also create good conditions for scientific research focused on issues such as: How should biomass plantations be located, designed and managed to affect biodiversity and landscape in a positive direction? What factors lead to increased risk of damage to the biomass crop (frost, insects, etc.) and thereby adversely affect both the profitability and landscape perception of the crop? The information from the corresponding scientific research should be used to regularly update the available growers' manuals and recommendations.

Environmental objectives

The cultivation of *Salix* on agricultural land can in different ways contribute to achieving several of the Swedish environmental objectives, such as 'Reduced Climate Impact', 'A Non-Toxic Environment', 'Zero Eutrophication', 'Good-Quality Groundwater', 'A Varied Agricultural Landscape' and 'A Rich Diversity of Plant and Animal Life' (Miljömålsrådet 2004, 2006). One problem, however, is that actions in these environmental objectives are likely to collide with each other (Naturvårdsverket, 1999). When planting energy crops on agricultural land to replace fossil fuels, tying up heavy metals and reduce nitrogen leaching, it is therefore a major challenge associated with the location, design and management of the plantation to additionally utilize the positive opportunities to benefit landscape, environment and cultural heritage values. The foregoing analysis showed that *Salix* plantations often can be located, designed and managed in such a way that they contribute to greater variation in the landscape, thereby encouraging or at least not conflicting with the environmental goals 'A Varied Agricultural Landscape' and 'A Rich Diversity of Plant and Animal Life'. However, there might well appear frictions between these environmental objectives and the environmental objective 'Reduced Climate Impact', which in the best way may be promoted by means of commercial plantations that achieve high biomass production and high carbon sequestration potentials. Maximisation of biomass production and carbon sequestration (through intensified management) should be weighed against its impact on biodiversity and cultural heritage, but if the positive opportunities of designing and managing the plantations in an environmentally friendly manner are fully exploited, serious conflicts might not arise. The environmental objectives 'A Non-Toxic Environment' and 'Good-Quality Groundwater' can be promoted by plantations with the purposes heavy metal decontamination and/or treatment of sewage water. These plantations are likely to be rather poor in species diversity (qualified scientific studies are lacking) and could thus counteract the environmental objectives 'A Varied Agricultural Landscape' and 'A Rich Diversity of Plant and Animal Life'. A mosaic of plantations with different purposes and therefore different design, management and size could be a matter of great diversity of conditions in which different organisms can thrive and great visual variation is provided (see above). Such a mosaic of

plantations would reduce the risk that the actions promoting different environmental objectives collide with each other. In addition, synergies could be achieved, if different types of crops are combined in a controlled way. For example, a not too large *Salix* plantation for soil decontamination could be established next to a poplar stand for energy purpose and with native trees between and around them, generating increased small-scale variation that would favour species diversity and landscape variation. It is possible that plantations of *Salix* (and other energy crops) could therefore become an important tool in the promotion of the Swedish environmental objectives, particularly if the positive possibilities for biodiversity and landscape/cultural heritage are utilized at maximum.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Commercial *Salix* plantations are today the vast majority of energy crop plantations in Sweden and these plantations are established and managed by purely economic reasons, which guides the location, design and management of plantations. If plantations would be established mainly for other reasons, such as phytoremediation to achieve the environmental objectives 'A Non-Toxic Environment' or 'Zero Eutrophication', it may be other factors that govern the location, design and management. A mosaic of plantations with different purposes and therefore different design and management have great potential to increase the number of environmental and cultural heritage values, in particular if the positive opportunities to favour these values are considered in each individual stand. Plantations of *Salix* can also be a tool to achieve the environmental objective 'Reduced Climate Impact' and the greatest amelioration effect is achieved with plantations located, designed and managed according to the commercial principles.

Plantations of *Salix* or other fast-growing deciduous trees on agricultural land can provide greater biodiversity at a landscape perspective, especially if they replace fields of cereals and spruce plantations grown on agricultural land in homogenous agricultural landscape. In addition, *Salix* plantations often have a positive effect on different soil characteristics compared with conventional farmed land. In particular, small-scale plantations can also raise the aesthetic values of landscape by adding variety and structure in an otherwise homogenous agricultural landscape. *Salix* plantations thus have a great potential to increase both biodiversity and landscape values, provided that one does not assume that these plantations are always a disruptive or "ugly" feature of the landscape. Some recommendations for the enhancement of the environmental, landscape and cultural heritage values of *Salix* plantations (see also Weih 2008):

- Plant near the native (deciduous) woods or establish "islands" with native hardwoods in connection with the *Salix* plantation;
- Harvest parts of the plantation in different years;
- Plant several smaller stands adjacent to each other with harvests in different years, instead of one large plantation;

- Plant various species or varieties (preferably of different gender) in the same stand, but in different sections (e.g., parallel "strips"), each with its own species/variety;
- Apply chemical weed control (herbicides) only in connection with the establishment of new plantations;
- Adjust the fertilisation regime to the growth rate of the stand;
- Leave buffer zones without any crop or with native vegetation in the edges of plantations;
- Avoid *Salix* plantations in areas of high nature conservation (biodiversity) and cultural heritage values;
- Try to plan harvest actions to be performed only during the period of frozen ground;
- Try to plan, design and manage the plantations so that they promote great variation in the landscape.

With respect to the location of plantations, no major conflict was found between the commercial, environmental and landscape/cultural heritage perspectives on *Salix* cultivation on agricultural land, as long as the stands are not planted in areas with protection status for nature conservation and/or cultural heritage. Synergies can be achieved if the plantations are situated near natural forests. The most serious contradictions with respect to the design and management of plantations are expected between the commercial perspective on one hand and the environmental and landscape/cultural heritage perspective on the other hand. The fertilisation of *Salix* plantations with waste water and sludge is advantageous from a commercial perspective, but can reduce the environmental and landscape benefits. *Salix* plantations can be located, designed and managed in such a way that they promote, or at least do not conflict with the Swedish environmental objectives 'A Varied Agricultural Landscape' and 'A Rich Diversity of Plant and Animal Life'. However, conflicts may arise between these two environmental objectives and the objective 'Reduced Climate Impact'.

The responses to a questionnaire to, *inter alia*, authorities, farmer and nature conservation organisations suggests a number of misconceptions or unjustified fears about what *Salix* plantations are, how they affect environment and landscape, and what conditions that apply for growing *Salix*. Despite the fact that the measures on how to raise the environmental and landscape benefits of *Salix* plantations have been well known for quite a long time, the positive possibilities for environment (e.g., biodiversity), landscape and cultural heritage are rarely utilised in the practical cultivation of this crop. A key to addressing these problems is to increase knowledge of the various interest groups and involved authorities, and to improve communication between them. Dissemination of information should be made by Growers' manuals (cf. Gustafsson *et al.* 2007), "guidelines" or recommendations, which stress the importance of the environmental and landscape aspects, and that give practical advice on how plantations should be located, designed and managed on how to best take advantage of the positive opportunities to promote environment and landscape (Weih 2008). The recommendations and Growers' manuals should be easily available to farmers, authorities and the public. Possibly also some form of financial compensation to farmers to offset the reduced income caused by the consideration of environmental / landscape aspects could stimulate the growers' interest in environmentally sound plantations. Very important, however, is that – towards the authorities, stakeholders

and the public – highlight the positive aspects and opportunities associated with *Salix* plantations, especially if compared with options such as conventional cereal cropping or fallow land.

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Short Rotation Crops for Bioenergy Systems

Task Benefits:

Membership of the Task provides links to overseas experts involved in short rotation crop bioenergy systems and facilitates contacts with the international bioenergy community especially within the many tasks of IEA Bioenergy

Task Activities:

- Annual conference
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- Case studies
- Newsletters
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- Brazil
- Canada
- Italy
- New Zealand
- The Netherlands
- The United Kingdom
- The United States of America
- Sweden

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